

Press Release June 2024

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators organizes international conference about open science and open education

On June 7, 2024, the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project held a hybrid international workshop on “Open Science and Open Education” at the School of Business Sciences (ESCE) of the Polytechnic University of Setúbal (IPS). This event was attended by several project partners, as well as representatives of other international alliances and guests, highlighting the E³UDRES² alliance's commitment to promoting innovation and collaboration between European higher education institutions, and stimulating open science and open education practices.

Funded by the European Commission through the Horizon Europe program, the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project is aligned with European priorities, emphasizing the importance of Open Science, Open Innovation, Open Education and Open Resources.

During the event, several relevant themes were addressed, emphasizing the importance of Open Science, Open Innovation, Open Education and Open Resources. Discussions involved topics such as the benefits of the European Open Science Cloud, the role of digital tools in facilitating open science, challenges and experiences in implementing open science practices, open license management, open pedagogies, the impact of emerging technologies on education, and innovative projects aimed at promoting open science and collaboration between European higher education institutions, thus providing a reflection on future collaborations and strategies to strengthen open science and education in Europe.

The event brought together a diverse range of experts, enriching the exchange of knowledge and reinforcing the importance of collaboration between academic institutions, thus reaffirming the importance of cooperation and the promotion of open science and education practices, consolidating the position of the E³UDRES² platform in European higher education.

The conference was attended by leading figures in the field of open science and open education, such as Luís Coelho, professor at IPS and coordinator of the Ent-r-e-novators project, Karel Luyben, president of the European Open Science Cloud Association, Silviu Vert, Radu VasIU and Diana Andone from the Polytechnic University of Timisoara (Romania), Tassilo Pellegrini from St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences (Austria), Sarah de Coninck from University Colleges Leuven Limburg (Belgium), Sílvia Roda Couvaneiro from Polytechnic University of Setúbal (Portugal), Antónia Correia, from the University of Minho (Portugal), Joana Boavida-Portugal from MARE (Portugal), and Pedro Manuel Antão from INCITIES project, Michelle Perello from EXPER project and Irina Lungu and Marcello Costantini on behalf of BI4E project.

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